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It is a pleasure and a privilege to have the honour to be a part of this issue of QIJMHS. It has always been the priority of QIUP and the Medical Faculty, in particular, to encourage and support staff to enhance the research activities in the university. We need to instill a research culture and the production of this journal is a testimony to this. The faculty of medicine targets by 2020 almost 90% of the preclinical staffs will hold a PhD qualification. This will surpass the national target of 60%. With the expansion of the faculties to include new programs, this will see an increasing trend in research activities.

The aim of having this QIJMHS is to showcase the research works by our staff through the online mode as this will have a far-reaching benefit to share with the health industry. Even though most of the research done will not be commercialized but the sharing of new information will still have a spillover effect in the health sector. For, commercialization, one must focus on applied research but one must not forget fundamental research. To gain access to funds and grants, one must prioritise according to the National priority areas. We must encourage collaborative research to achieve this. We must encourage staff into this research culture and subsequently publish their work. Universities must support this culture by recognizing their staffs work through incentives and benefits.

In Quest University we are very grateful to the University Council Chairman Dato' Sri Dr. Vijay Eswaran, the Vice Chancellor Dato' Professor Dr. Raman Narayanasamy and the Chief Operating Officer Mr. Nicholas Goh Kow Chin for their encouragement and undivided support of the research culture in the university and also making this issue of the journal is a success. Kudos and a big note of appreciation and thanks to the editorial board for their unrelenting effort in producing this journal, to the peer reviewers and language editors for their efforts and to all those who are directly or indirectly involved to make this issue of the QIJMHS a success. THANK YOU all.

Regards,

Co-Editor-in-Chief

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Competing interests

None declared.

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